

Assessing feature importance for forecasting soil moisture in subarctic regions using gridded historical and forecasted climate data

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ABSTRACT

Continuous monitoring of soil moisture (SM) is essential in precision agriculture for effective irrigation management. However, SM forecasting in subarctic environments remains relatively unexplored. In this study, we forecast SM at a 30-centimeter soil depth over a 7-day period using Random Forest (RF) model. Two scenarios were evaluated: (a) relying solely on historical data (HIST), and (b) using forecasted environmental data along with recent SM measurements to predict SM levels iteratively, integrating next-day forecasts with current SM data (FORENV). The input features included daily gridded climate data (air temperature- T_{air} , relative humidity-RH, wind speed-WS, precipitation-P, and reference evapotranspiration-ET₀), soil-vegetation (SV) features (gridded soil temperature- T_{soil} and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index-NDVI) and lagged SM values. These data were gathered from six sites under different land covers in subarctic regions (Finland-Tyrnava) over approximately two growing seasons (July or August 2022–September 2023), yielding about 430 daily observations per site. The analysis showed that FORENV outperformed HIST for up to four days into the forecast horizon, highlighting the value of including forecasted variables for improved accuracy during these initial lead times. Longer lead times proved more site-dependent, influenced by the stability of historical SM correlations. Pearson correlation and RF-based stepwise forward feature selection revealed that using only lagged SM data, or combining it with SV features, yielded the most accurate forecasts. For instance, at $t + 7$ and across all case studies combined, models incorporating LaggedSM_SV achieved the lowest RMSE ($0.019 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$) and highest R^2 (0.67), followed by All_inputs (RMSE: $0.022 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$, R^2 : 0.61), and LaggedSM (RMSE: $0.025 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$, R^2 : 0.46). Daily P and RH exhibited consistently low correlations with subsurface SM, likely due to near-saturated soil conditions in many subarctic sites that buffer infiltration and reduce immediate sensitivity to these parameters. Overall, our results demonstrate that robust SM forecasts can be achieved even with limited data, making this approach particularly valuable in subarctic regions with near-saturated soil conditions or other areas where climate and soil-vegetation data may be sparse.

1. Introduction

Recent advancements in precision agriculture focus on optimizing the relationship between soil, water, and crop environments to improve crop growth. Water, in particular, plays a crucial role in plant productivity, and precision irrigation has emerged as an essential method for enhancing water use efficiency (Yu et al., 2021). This targeted application of water maximizes crop yields while reducing the ecological impact of agriculture (Kamienski et al., 2019). By minimizing water use, precision irrigation also reduces energy costs, as less power is needed to operate irrigation systems (Abrishambaf et al., 2020; Fernández García

et al., 2016). With agriculture accounting for 70–80 % of global fresh-water consumption (Grafton et al., 2018), the need for optimized water use strategies is urgent, particularly in regions affected by climate variability (Hashemy Shahdany et al., 2015).

Despite Finland's abundance of water resources (Canton, 2021), recent droughts (2002–2003, 2018–2019) during growing season, highlighted vulnerabilities in the agricultural sector, with significant losses in crop production (Silander & Järvinen, 2004; YLE, 2018). These droughts, combined with projections of increased temperatures and precipitation variability, underscore the importance of improved drought monitoring. Moreover, given Finland's limited exposure to

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drought, systematic national drought policies are lacking (Ahopelto et al., 2023), which presents a challenge for agricultural water management in the future.

Soil moisture (SM), the water content within the soil accessible to plant roots, is a critical determinant of plant health and productivity (Jensen & Allen, 2016). Each type of soil has an optimal SM range for plant growth, ensuring that plants can effectively absorb water (Rawls et al., 1991; Van Genuchten, 1980). In precision agriculture, maintaining SM within this optimal range is essential for effective irrigation scheduling, and the advent of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies has significantly improved our ability to monitor SM in real-time (García et al., 2020; Kamiński et al., 2019). Given the complexity of soil moisture dynamics and the need for models capable of handling large and varied datasets, the Random Forest (RF) model has been widely adopted in environmental prediction studies (Adeyemi et al., 2018; Dubois et al., 2021; Gumiere et al., 2020; Karandish & Šimůnek, 2016; Masrur Ahmed et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023). For this study, RF was chosen for SM forecasting due to its ability to handle nonlinear relationships, suitability for datasets with limited temporal coverage (e.g., those spanning only a few growing seasons such as ours with two growing seasons), ease of hyperparameter tuning, and consistent performance across various environmental applications. While deep learning models have shown promise in SM forecasting (Cai et al., 2019; Kashyap et al., 2021; Kochhar et al., 2022; Masrur Ahmed et al., 2021; Togneri et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023), RF (Acharya et al., 2021; Caranza et al., 2021; Gumiere et al., 2020; Hedley et al., 2013; Pan JinJing et al., 2019; Togneri et al., 2022; Wang & Fu, 2023) was preferred in current study due to its simpler implementation and suitability for the available dataset. Moreover, RF has demonstrated superior performance compared to other traditional models such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) in related studies (Acharya et al., 2021; Gill et al., 2006; Gumiere et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2006; Maia et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Zaman & McKee, 2014).

To forecast SM, a variety of factors must be considered, including meteorological parameters such as air temperature (T_{air}), relative humidity (RH), wind speed (WS), precipitation (P), solar radiation (SR), and types of evapotranspiration (both reference-ET₀ and potential-PET). Additionally, plant characteristics such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), soil attributes like soil temperature (T_{soil}), and historical SM data also play a role. Temporal factors (e.g., year, day of the year, hour), along with Fourier transformations, have been used to capture interannual variability in SM (Pan et al., 2019). Geographical details such as latitude and longitude are often incorporated into SM forecasting models (Yu et al., 2021). Past studies have leveraged in-situ climate data (Acharya et al., 2021; Gill et al., 2006; Hong et al., 2016; Kashyap et al., 2021; Maia et al., 2022; Ren et al., 2023; Zaman & McKee, 2014), as well as forcing climate data such as FLUXNET datasets (Li et al., 2022; Pan JinJing et al., 2019). However, in regions with limited in-situ data availability, relying solely on observational datasets can hinder accurate SM forecasting due to their sparse spatial coverage and lack of temporal continuity (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021; Ochsner et al., 2013). Climate reanalysis datasets such as ERA5, which integrate observational data with model outputs to provide globally consistent and gap-filled datasets, offer a practical solution to this limitation. These datasets are particularly valuable in subarctic regions, where the harsh environment and logistical challenges often lead to sparse monitoring networks (Lan et al., 2022; Virman et al., 2023). This study, therefore, explores the use of reanalysis climate data to bridge this gap and improve SM forecasting in data-scarce regions.

Existing research has rarely explored the incorporation of vegetation indices like NDVI in SM forecasting, resulting in a significant gap in the literature. While studies such as those by Maia et al. (2022) and Togneri et al. (2022) have begun exploring the potential of NDVI in estimating or predicting soil moisture, these works primarily focus on static or monthly NDVI data rather than integrating historical and forecasted

daily NDVI for horizon-based forecasting. Incorporating vegetation dynamics with historical and forecasted NDVI can provide valuable insights into SM fluctuations, as plant health directly influences water uptake and ET processes (Jung et al., 2017). Our study tried to bridge this gap by leveraging both historical gap-filled NDVI and forecasted NDVI to forecast SM over a seven-day horizon, offering a novel approach to SM forecasting. Previous studies on SM predictions were limited to static models that could forecast SM based on data available up to current day (t) (Acharya et al., 2021; Gill et al., 2006; Kashyap et al., 2021; Maia et al., 2022; Ren et al., 2023; Zaman & McKee, 2014), but these models often failed to account for changes in weather conditions between day t and the forecast day. For instance, significant rainfall events occurring after the current day could invalidate the predictions, as static models did not incorporate real-time weather updates (Hong et al., 2016). Fortunately, advancements in weather forecasting technologies have enabled more accurate and accessible meteorological forecasts (Zippenfenig, 2023), allowing for more dynamic models that integrate forecasted weather data for improved SM predictions. Despite these developments, many existing studies continue to rely heavily on historical data, highlighting a gap in utilizing forecasted weather data for real-time SM forecasting.

Limited research has been conducted on the significance of various features in SM forecasting. Pan JinJing et al., 2019 carried out a series of experiments where they added explaining variables one by one. The results showed that historical SM data, coupled with temporal factors such as year, day of the year, and hour, outperformed other variables. Another study by Togneri et al. (2022) used a stepwise forward feature selection method and found that including historical SM, a context-aware index, and P alone could lead to robust SM forecasts. Interestingly, widely considered parameters such as ET, crop phenology, and soil hydraulic properties did not improve forecast performance. Yu et al. (2021) assessed different parameters for SM forecasting, including historical SM at various depths, climate data, and geographic details such as latitude and longitude, using Pearson correlation analysis. They found that P and SR had negligible correlations and thus excluded them from model inputs. However, despite these insights, there remains a gap in understanding how different combinations of historical and forecasted variables can be optimized for various land cover types and climates, particularly in data-scarce regions.

Previous research has seldom focused on the integration of vegetation indices such as NDVI in SM forecasting, leaving a notable gap in literature. Additionally, while numerous studies have utilized in-field climate data for SM prediction, there remains a significant challenge in regions where such data are scarce. Most of the aforementioned literature relied heavily on historical climate records, creating a substantial gap in leveraging forecasted weather data for SM forecasting. Furthermore, the forecasting of SM in humid regions has not been extensively explored. There has been limited focus on identifying the most efficient combination of feature groups for SM forecasting, particularly in diverse environmental contexts. To address these gaps, the current study aims to achieve several objectives. First, it assesses the efficacy of gridded climate data for forecasting SM. Second, the study incorporates NDVI as a proxy for plant phenological parameters in SM prediction. Third, it analyzes the impact of various potential parameters on SM within subarctic ecosystems. Fourth, the study evaluates the influence of forecasted climate parameters on SM prediction and compares the outcomes with those derived solely from historical data. Finally, the study assesses the performance of RF- and Pearson correlation-based models using different feature group datasets to determine the most effective parameters in SM forecasting.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. In-situ SM monitoring sites and observations

Six SM monitoring sites within the Temmes basin in northern Finland

were selected for this study, covering three land cover types: Crop, Forest, and Forest_Peatland (Fig. 1). DECENTLAB (DL-TRS12-001) soil moisture sensors were installed at these sites to measure SM at a 30 cm soil depth with a temporal resolution of 10 min. These sensors employ 70 MHz frequency capacitance technology and can measure SM content ranging from 0.000 to 1.000 m³.m⁻³ at a resolution of 0.001 m³.m⁻³. According to manufacturer specifications, accuracy may vary based on soil medium, with a potential maximum deviation of ±0.03 m³.m⁻³ (±3.00 % Volumetric Water Content-VWC) under generic calibration conditions. The sensors also record soil temperature, electrical conductivity, and battery voltage, transmitting all data via LoRaWAN technology. Although a generic factory calibration was used, the sensors were installed following the manufacturer’s guidelines to minimize site-specific biases.

The SM data utilized in this study span from July or August 2022 to September 2023 (~430 daily data points per site), reflecting the date of

sensor installation and data availability. To transform the 10-minute readings into daily data for subsequent analyses, a simple averaging approach was employed. This daily aggregation helps smooth short-term fluctuations and provides a stable input for the forecasting models. Fig. 1 offers a brief description of each SM monitoring site in the study area.

- I. Crop A: In this cropland, the SM sensor is installed in fertile organic topsoil, conducive to agricultural productivity. This parcel of agricultural land was dedicated to cultivating barley during the monitoring period (2022–2023). The monitoring system was located at a corner of the field, adjacent to an agricultural drainage ditch that served as a boundary between two fields. This ditch was noted to be overgrown with weeds and other vegetation. Moreover, the agricultural field was bordered on one side by forested land. It was also observed that there was

Fig. 1. Research area and distribution of SM monitoring stations.

no additional drainage system installed near the SM monitoring system's location, indicating a reliance on the existing natural and agricultural drainage features.

- II. Crop B: At the installation depth of the SM sensor, the soil profile was predominantly made of organic topsoil, recognized for its high fertility and suitability for agricultural activities. During the year of installation in 2022 and continuing through the monitoring period in 2023, the land was employed for either grazing livestock or cultivating fodder crops. The sensor was strategically positioned next to a drainage ditch, serving as a boundary between two agricultural fields.
- III. Forest C: In this case study, unlike others, there was no drainage ditch in the vicinity. The soil profile consisted of a peat layer at the top, transitioning to a coarse-grained sandy soil around the depth at which the SM sensor was installed. The location of interest was also nestled within a dense forest characterized by the presence of large trees.
- IV. Forest D: The installation process of the SM instrument for this site revealed a soil profile that was primarily coarse-grained, featuring a blend of sand and numerous big and small rocks. The surrounding forest at the installation site showcased a diversity of tree life, ranging from young saplings to towering, ancient trees. Despite the presence of a drainage ditch in proximity to the monitoring location, it proved to be largely inefficient, filled with rocks and its depth obstructed by sediments. This condition posed challenges for effective water management in the vicinity.
- V. Forest Peatland E: The SM monitoring system was located in an area characterized by sparsely populated, very young trees. The soil profile at this site consisted of a peat layer on the surface, underlain by a blend of organic materials and sandy soil. Additionally, a drainage ditch was situated approximately 20 m from the point of interest, potentially affecting the hydrological conditions of the site.
- VI. Forest Peatland F: The SM sensor installation site was situated in an open, marshy peatland area. While the nearby forest was dense, it was not populated by young or small trees. The upper layer of soil at this site was a combination of peat and organic materials, transitioning into a mixture of sandy clay soil at the depth where the SM sensor was installed. Additionally, a drainage ditch was in close proximity to the point of interest, at a distance of less than 50 m.

2.2. Climate and NDVI data

In addition to local SM sensor data described in the previous section, satellite and gridded weather data (Table 1) were employed in this study to address the scarcity of in-situ data in our study areas. Historical data used in this study was sourced from historical OM, derived from ERA5 (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021; Tarek et al., 2020) via Open-Meteo (OM) (Amoura et al., 2023; Defalque et al., 2024; Depoortere et al., 2024; Perez Garcia et al., 2024; Romero Rodríguez et al., 2023; Zhang, 2023), maintaining a consistent spatial resolution of 9–11 km. These

parameters, including T_{air} , ET_0 , RH , P , T_{soil} , and WS , were critical for capturing SM dynamics, particularly T_{soil} and WS , which were unavailable in the FMI_1km dataset described in the following.

OM uses its archived forecasts to address the five-day delay in historical OM data. This functionality allows access to forecast outputs generated in the past, effectively filling the gap for the most recent five days preceding the provision of historical OM. It is important to note that the archived forecast data stored in OM is limited to the most recent three months. For this study, these archived forecasts were used to ensure continuity in historical climate records and evaluating SM forecasting results in FORENV scenario discussed in section 2.4.

Additionally, OM supplies forecast OM data for up to 16 days into the future by default, though this study utilized only a seven-day forecast horizon to align with the objectives of short-term SM forecasting. The forecasts integrate outputs from advanced weather models, including ICON (Icosahedral Nonhydrostatic), GFS & HRRR (Global Forecast System and High-Resolution Rapid Refresh), MeteoFrance, ERA5, MSM & GSM (Japan Meteorological Agency Mesoscale Model and Global Spectral Model), MET NORDIC, GEM (Global Environmental Multiscale Model), GFS GRAPES, ACCESS-G (Australian Community Climate and Earth-System Simulator – Global), and COSMO 2I & 5 M (high-resolution models focusing on European weather patterns, developed by the Consortium for Small-scale Modeling).

For each location worldwide, OM dynamically selects and combines the best-performing weather models (e.g., ICON, GFS, MET NORDIC) with individual spatial resolutions ranging from 1 to 25 km, ensuring that its data reflects the most precise and location-specific weather predictions available. These same models were used to provide the archived forecasts to fill the five-day gap in historical OM and to provide seven-day forecast OM data, ensuring consistency in the data sources and methodologies. The OM (<https://open-meteo.com/>) can be accessed for additional details about the forecast data and the methodology behind the integration of various weather models.

The FMI_1km dataset, with its high spatial resolution of 1 km (Aalto et al., 2016; PIRINEN1 et al., 2022), was used as a benchmark for validating the accuracy of historical OM in our study region. FMI_1km includes key variables like T_{air} , RH , P , and ET_0 , which allowed for a comparative evaluation. However, its exclusion of T_{soil} and WS meant it could not fully meet the requirements of this study, necessitating the complementary use of historical OM.

By combining historical OM, archived forecasts, forecast OM, and FMI_1km datasets (Table 1), this study ensured robust SM forecasting with comprehensive temporal and spatial coverage. Historical OM provided historical climate data, while the archived forecasts addressed the five-day delay in the historical OM data, and forecast OM supplied the seven-day forecast period. Additionally, FMI_1km validated the performance of historical OM in capturing local conditions, complementing the overall dataset reliability.

Historical NDVI data, serving as a proxy for SM fluctuations, were obtained from MODIS satellite imagery at a 500 m spatial resolution. Due to frequent cloud cover, particularly in subarctic environments, continuous daily NDVI retrievals were not always possible. To address this, we implemented a three-step gap-filling procedure (Fig. A1)

Table 1

Overview of climate and NDVI datasets used for SM forecasting. The spatial resolution range reflects the integration of multiple weather models (e.g., ICON, GFS, MET NORDIC) utilized in the OM dataset to fill gaps for historical OM's five-day delay and provide forecast data for up to seven days.

Dataset name	Source	Spatial resolution	Spatial coverage	Temporal coverage	Variables used
Historical OM	ECMWF embedded in Open-Meteo(https://open-meteo.com/)	9–11 km	Global	1950-present	T_{air} , T_{soil} , RH , P , WS , ET_0
Forecast OM	Open-Meteo (https://open-meteo.com/)	1–25 km	Global	Recent 3 months (archived forecasts) and 16-day forecast	T_{air} , T_{soil} , RH , P , WS , ET_0
FMI_1km	Finnish Meteorological Institute (Gridded observations – Finnish Meteorological Institute (ilmatieteenlaitos.fi))	1 km	Finland	1961-present	T_{air} , RH , P , ET_0
MODIS	NASA (https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/data/)	500 m	Global	2000-present	NDVI

designed to reconstruct a consistent and representative NDVI time series as follows:

- I. For days with missing NDVI data, linear interpolation was employed to estimate the values. This method calculates intermediate NDVI values by assuming a linear trend between the nearest available cloud-free observations on either side of the gap. This approach ensured the continuity of the time series while avoiding abrupt jumps caused by data gaps (Miklashevich et al., 2019; Moreno-Martínez et al., 2018).
- II. To enhance the reliability of the interpolated values and mitigate errors from transient clouds or atmospheric effects, we integrated MODIS 8-day composite NDVI products. These composite images, generated by aggregating multiple observations over an 8-day window, provide more robust and stable representations of vegetation conditions. The interpolated daily NDVI values were calibrated against the corresponding 8-day composite values to ensure alignment with the broader temporal trends. This step improved the consistency and reliability of the reconstructed NDVI data.
- III. To further refine the dataset, a three-day moving average filter was applied to the calibrated NDVI values. This smoothing process minimized short-term variability and residual noise, resulting in a time series that more accurately represented underlying vegetation dynamics rather than transient fluctuations caused by sensor noise or atmospheric disturbances.

Through this three-step process of linear interpolation, composite-based calibration, and smoothing, we produced a continuous, high-quality daily NDVI dataset. This enhanced NDVI record enabled more reliable analysis of vegetation health and, by extension, improved SM forecasting capability.

For forecasting NDVI, we employed a Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average with Exogenous Variables (SARIMAX) model. The SARIMAX model extends the ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) model by incorporating both seasonal components and exogenous variables. The SARIMAX model integrates these variables into the forecasting process, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis that considers the impact of external factors on vegetation dynamics (Miklashevich et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2022). In the current study, SARIMAX utilized historical NDVI and climate parameters from the last six years during the growing season as inputs. These datasets served to forecast SM for the subsequent day, a process that we iteratively applied for a 7-day forecasting horizon.

2.3. Random Forest model

The RF model is an ensemble learning technique for regression and classification that creates multiple decision trees during training and averages their predictions for the final output. This approach reduces overfitting, common in individual trees, by leveraging a diverse set of decision trees, trained on different dataset segments. According to (Breiman, 2001; Louppe, 2014), the RF algorithm employs hierarchical decisions from root to terminal nodes, with each step guided by a set of rules. To ensure diversity and reduce correlation among trees, RF employs bootstrap sampling with replacement, such that each tree is trained on an in-bag subset representing, on average, around 63 % of the original data. The remaining out-of-bag samples (approximately 37 %) are then used to estimate prediction error and provide an unbiased error estimate. This methodology, as highlighted by (Qu et al., 2019), allows for an unbiased error estimation. RF employs a recursive binary splitting strategy, optimizing homogeneity in splits and continuing until nodes meet a minimum observation count. For regression, it averages decision tree outputs for consensus-based predictions.

As earlier mentioned, this study utilized daily SM observations and associated environmental parameters from six subarctic sites (Crop,

Forest and Forest_Peatland) spanning approximately two growing seasons (July or August 2022–September 2023). One of the main objectives was capturing local soil-vegetation dynamics, including the role of NDVI as a proxy for plant phenology and evaluating predictive performance within each site's unique conditions. Due to this emphasis on site-specific insights rather than temporal or spatial generalization and limited temporal coverage, time-series-specific validation approaches (e.g., TimeSeriesSplit or leave-site-out cross-validation) were not feasible. Instead, the data for each site were randomly split into 75 % training and 25 % testing sets. We acknowledge that this random splitting approach may introduce temporal leakage, as time-dependent correlations could lead to overly optimistic results. However, given the short time span of the observations and the site-specific nature of the study, this limitation is partially mitigated. Future studies with longer temporal datasets could employ stricter time-based cross-validation approaches to address this concern fully.

The training portion was further refined using a conventional K-fold cross-validation ($K = 10$) via Python's Scikit-learn's GridSearchCV to fine-tune hyperparameters ($n_estimators = [50, 100, 150, 200]$, $max_depth = [0, 10, 20, 30]$, $min_samples_split = [2, 5, 10]$, $min_samples_leaf = [1, 2, \text{and } 4]$). After running the grid search with 10-fold cross-validation, the best-performing hyperparameters for different sites were mostly identified as: $n_estimators = 200$, $max_depth = \text{None}$ (allowing trees to grow without depth restriction), $min_samples_split = 2$, and $min_samples_leaf = 1$. Although a time-series-based CV might better capture temporal dependencies, data constraints and the study's objectives led us to select this simpler approach. The initial test set served as a primary evaluation dataset, allowing a preliminary assessment of model performance under historical conditions. Subsequently, from within this test dataset, we identified a specific six-month window where the archived forecast data were available, defining this period as the "Archived-Forecast Subset". It should be noted that, as OM provides the archived forecasts only for the recent three months (Table 1), we were able to accumulate around six months of archived forecasts during the experiments' conduction. This subset facilitated a realistic evaluation of the FORENV scenario, as explained in Section 2.4.

2.3.1. Feature importance analysis

In this study, we adopted a two-step strategy to identify the most influential predictors for SM forecasting. Unlike conventional approaches that rely on intrinsic RF variable importance metrics (e.g., Gini importance or permutation importance), we used a combination of linear correlation analysis and performance-based incremental feature group selection. This allowed us to systematically determine how different sets of features affected the predictive capability of the model, rather than depending solely on internally computed importance scores.

First, we computed the Pearson correlation coefficients (Datta et al., 2022; Togneri et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2021) between each predictor (climate parameters, NDVI, and current/lagged SM) and future SM (from SM_{t+1} to SM_{t+7}). Pearson correlation, while limited to linear relationships, provides a straightforward initial indication of how strongly a given predictor is associated with future SM. Correlation coefficients range from -1 (perfect negative relationship) to $+1$ (perfect positive relationship), with values close to zero suggesting weak or no linear association. Moreover, p-value indicates whether a feature shows a statistically significant relationship (typically lower than 0.05) with SM. This preliminary assessment helped identify potential drivers of SM variability but did not capture nonlinearities or interactions among variables.

After establishing a baseline understanding of linear relationships, we employed a stepwise forward feature group selection process using the RF model. Instead of calculating RF's built-in importance measures, we partitioned the input variables into distinct groups based on climate, soil-vegetation (SV), and historical SM parameters (Table 2), and then gradually introduced these groups into the RF model. By comparing changes in model performance as groups were added, we assessed which

Table 2
Different feature groups datasets are used to determine the most significant features in SM forecasting.

Feature group dataset	Features
Climate	T_{air} , RH, ET0, WS and P
SV (soil-vegetation)	T_{soil} and NDVI
LaggedSM	in-situ $SM_{t/t-1}$
SV_Climate	SV + Climate groups
LaggedSM_SV	LaggedSM + SV groups
LaggedSM_Climate	LaggedSM + Climate groups
All_inputs(primary dataset)	all features

sets of features provided the greatest improvement. This approach, detailed in Section 3.4, facilitated the examination of each group’s predictive capacity across three distinct SM lead times: $t + 1$ (beginning of the period), $t + 4$ (middle of the period), and $t + 7$ (end of the period).

Potential multicollinearity could influence how certain variables contribute to model performance. Highly correlated predictors might transmit similar information to the model, making it difficult to isolate the effect of any single variable. Acknowledging this, we interpreted the results in terms of feature groups rather than individual predictors, thus reducing the risk of overstating the importance of any single correlated variable. By evaluating the incremental improvement in model accuracy when adding each feature group, we anticipated a more stable and reliable indication of the variables’ collective importance.

2.4. Forecasting SM

This study implemented two distinct methodologies (Fig. 2) to predict SM over a seven-day forecast horizon.

Under HIST, the RF model utilized only historical environmental parameters, current SM, and one-day lagged SM data to predict SM for the subsequent seven days. This scenario provided a baseline for understanding intrinsic SM dynamics without forward-looking climate information.

The FORENV scenario integrated the archived forecasted climate data into the SM prediction process. At the time of analysis, the archived forecast data from OM were only available for the preceding six months. Given that the key crop growth season in Finland spans May–September (Ghag et al., 2024), we focused on the portion of the testing period during which these forecasted inputs were accessible. As earlier mentioned, from the initial test dataset, we extracted the observations corresponding to these six months of available archived forecast data, defining this selection as “Archived-Forecast Subset”. In the FORENV scenario, the RF model used the forthcoming day’s forecasted environmental parameters alongside the current SM measurement each day,

iteratively generating day-by-day forecasts over the seven-day horizon. This approach offered a realistic evaluation of the model’s capabilities under genuinely forward-looking conditions.

To ensure a fair comparison, we identified the same set of dates in the HIST test dataset that comprised Archived-Forecast Subset. Evaluating both scenarios on these identical observations ensured that any differences in performance metrics reflected the integration of forecasted environmental data rather than differences in timing or conditions. Consequently, while the initial test set provided a preliminary evaluation, the final metrics reported in this study were calculated specifically from the Archived-Forecast Subset. This choice allowed us to highlight the added value of incorporating genuine forecasted inputs and present a more realistic depiction of the model’s operational performance during the period of interest.

Root mean square error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2) were selected to evaluate the performance of the scenarios. RMSE measures the average magnitude of the prediction error (Kelley & Lai, 2011; Willmott, 1982) and is calculated as the square root of the mean of squared differences between predicted and observed values. Lower RMSE values indicate better model performance, as they reflect smaller prediction errors. R^2 quantifies the proportion of variance in the observed data that is explained by the model (Chicco et al., 2021; Di Buccianico, 2008). It ranges from 0 to 1, where values closer to 1 indicate a better fit, meaning the model explains most of the variability in the data.

3. Results

3.1. Climate and NDVI data evaluation

The performance of the historical OM data was assessed for its suitability in forecasting SM using FMI_1km data as a reference due to the lack of in-situ soil and climate data for the intended sites (Table 3). It should be noted that the assessment was restricted to parameters common to both the historical OM and FMI_1km datasets. The average metrics across all stations indicated that the historical OM data for T_{air} , RH, and ET0 could serve as suitable alternatives to those of the FMI_1km dataset. Conversely, historical OM’s P showed low performance when

Table 3
Evaluation of historical OM using FMI_1km as reference across all stations.

	T_{air}	RH	P	ET0
RMSE	1.2°C	4.61 %	2.88 mm	0.2 mm.day ⁻¹
R^2	0.98	0.87	0.27	0.98

Fig. 2. Diagrams of HIST (SM forecasting based on historical data only) and FORENV (SM forecasting based forecasted environmental alongside recent SM data) scenarios. The terms abbreviated are OM (gridded climate parameters obtained from Open-Meteo datasets), NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index), SM (Soil Moisture), RF (Random Forest model), t (current day), $t-1$ (previous day), $t + 1$, $t + 2$, etc. (subsequent days).

compared to FMI_1km. Thus, a Pearson correlation analysis compared historical OM and FMI_1km parameters with in-situ SM_{t+1} data, showing comparable average correlations across all stations for all parameters (Table 4). Therefore, the historical OM dataset can reliably be considered an alternative to FMI_1km for forecasting SM.

For SM forecasting, forecast OM was evaluated by historical OM climate data (Table 5). Specifically, the forecast T_{air} exhibited high accuracy with a low RMSE (0.63 °C) and a high R² value (0.98), indicating a strong correlation with observed values. Similarly, ET₀ and T_{soil} forecasts also demonstrated strong performance, with low RMSE values of 0.37 mm.day⁻¹ and 0.84 °C, respectively, and high R² values of 0.93 and 0.92. While RH and WS forecasts showed appropriate performance, with RMSE values of 3.97 % and 2.24 km.h⁻¹ and R² values of 0.88 and 0.63, respectively, P forecasts exhibited a moderate level of variability with an RMSE of 3.34 mm and an R² of 0.64.

The forecasted NDVI values using SARIMAX model were evaluated against observed NDVI values for the next 7 days (Fig. 3). For t + 1 and t + 2, the RMSE and R² values were quite low and high (around 0.95), respectively, indicating a strong correlation between the forecasted and actual NDVI. However, for t + 3 and t + 4, the RMSE values increased slightly (approximately 0.05), indicating slightly higher prediction errors compared to the first two days. The R² values also decreased but were still relatively high (about 0.65), indicating a moderate correlation. Subsequently, for t + 5 to t + 7, both the RMSE and R² values indicated decreasing prediction accuracy and correlation as the forecasting horizon increased.

3.2. Pearson correlation analysis

Fig. 4 indicates the Pearson correlation coefficients and two-tail significance test results between various environmental parameters and future in-situ SM across the six different sites. It should be noted that this experiment was conducted only for HIST, which can show the relations of historical input parameters with SM at different lead times, compared to FORENV, which is more suited to indicating the relationships only with next-day lead time SM. Hereafter, the correlation coefficients were regarded as the comparison criterion for features' importance as most of the features used in the study showed significant p-value (< 0.05) (Fig. 4).

The T_{air} correlation coefficients ranged from high to negligible across different sites, indicating varying degrees of association between T_{air} and future SM. Moreover, Crop sites generally exhibited higher correlations compared to Forest and Forest_Peatland sites. Correlations with RH were mostly negligible to low, suggesting weak associations with forecasted SM at all sites. Correlation coefficients for P were generally low to negligible across all sites, indicating limited influence on future SM levels. The ET₀ correlations ranged from minimal to moderate across sites, with Crop sites showing moderate to low associations, while Forest and Forest_Peatland sites exhibited low to minimal correlations. The WS correlations were generally low across all sites, indicating minimal influence on future SM levels. Strong correlations were observed between T_{soil} and future SM, particularly at Crop sites, suggesting a notable relationship between these two variables. The NDVI correlations with forecasted SM varied across sites, with Crop sites showing higher correlations compared to Forest and Forest_Peatland sites. Strong positive correlations were noticed between in-situ SM_{t/t-1} (current and lagged

Table 4
Pearson correlation analysis for historical OM and FMI_1km parameters against in-situ SM_{t+1}.

	FMI_1km	historical OM
T _{air} vs in-situ SM _{t+1}	0.31	0.34
RH vs in-situ SM _{t+1}	0.11	0.12
P vs in-situ SM _{t+1}	0.10	0.11
ET ₀ vs in-situ SM _{t+1}	0.20	0.22

Table 5
Forecasted against observed climate data evaluation.

	T _{air}	RH	P	WS	ET ₀	T _{soil}
RMSE	0.63 °C	3.97 %	3.34 mm	2.24 km.h ⁻¹	0.37 mm.day ⁻¹	0.84 °C
R ²	0.98	0.88	0.64	0.63	0.93	0.92

Fig. 3. SARIMAX forecasted against observed NDVI. “t” refers to the current day.

SM) and future SM, indicating a consistent relationship across all sites.

Overall, the correlations highlighted the complex interactions between environmental variables and forecasted SM dynamics in subarctic regions across different land use types, with Crop sites generally exhibiting stronger associations compared to Forest and Forest_Peatland sites.

3.3. SM forecast analysis

The trends observed in RMSE and R² values for SM forecasting by RF model varied across different scenarios and forecast lead times (Fig. 5). Specifically, RMSE values generally displayed an increasing trend as the forecast lead time increased. Conversely, R² values exhibited a decreasing trend over the same period.

FORENV generally demonstrated superior performance compared to HIST across most sites until t + 4. However, beyond t + 4, the performance of HIST and FORENV varied across different sites. For instance, at sites Forest C and Forest_Peatland E, FORENV continued to exhibit better accuracy compared to HIST even after t + 4. Conversely, at sites Crop B and Forest_Peatland F, the performance of HIST surpassed that of FORENV after t + 4. This transition occurred after t + 5 for site Forest D. Interestingly, site Crop A consistently demonstrated better performance under HIST for all lead times compared to FORENV.

3.4. Feature group selection

To identify the most effective input feature groups for SM forecasting, stepwise forward feature group selection was conducted using RF. As detailed in section 2.3.1, the primary dataset was subdivided into feature groups (Table 2). It should be noted that this experiment was conducted only for the HIST scenario, which can show the relations of historical input parameters with SM at different lead times, compared to FORENV, which is more suited to indicating the relationships only with next-day lead time SM.

Results in Fig. 6 showed that models trained on datasets incorporating LaggedSM data consistently achieved the highest accuracy across

Fig. 4. Pearson correlation analysis between lead time observed SM and HIST's predictors for each land cover. This figure contains the correlation coefficients alongside statistical significance denoted with stars including *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, and ***p < 0.001. Those with insignificant p-value (>0.05) were visualized by white color.

all evaluated lead times. Specifically, the LaggedSM_SV group outperformed other feature combinations, particularly at longer lead times. LaggedSM_SV group emerged as the most effective input group, which warranted further analysis into the individual contributions of SV parameters (T_{soil} and NDVI) when combined with LaggedSM (Table 6).

4. Discussion

4.1. OM dataset and SARIMAX outputs evaluation

Table 5 indicates the promising performance of the forecast OM data across multiple climate variables. While forecasted P and WS showed a moderate accuracy, the high accuracy and strong correlation observed for other parameters such as T_{air}, ETO, T_{soil} and RH suggested that the forecast OM data can be reliably used for SM forecasting tasks. Moreover, the NDVI forecast accuracy decreased with the increase of the forecasting horizon, highlighting the SARIMAX model's proficiency in the short horizon of NDVI forecasting while also emphasizing the inherent challenges associated with longer-term predictions (Fig. 3). This behavior might be attributed to the temporal autocorrelation in NDVI values, which is relatively strong in the short term, enabling the SARIMAX model to effectively capture trends. However, as the

forecasting horizon extends, the autocorrelation weakens, and environmental factors like unpredictable climate events, changes in soil moisture, and plant phenology introduce nonlinearity and noise that challenge the model's accuracy. Additionally, SARIMAX, being a linear statistical model, assumes static relationships between predictors and the target variable (Miklashevich et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2022). In reality, vegetation growth processes are dynamic and influenced by complex interactions among multiple environmental variables, which evolve over time. These limitations explain the progressive decline in prediction accuracy for longer lead times, as the model struggles to accommodate increasing uncertainties and nonlinear behavior in NDVI dynamics.

4.2. Feature importance evaluation

The results of the correlation analysis (Fig. 4) shed light on the intricate relationship of various environmental parameters, and current and lagged SM with the future SM across different land covers.

The correlations between T (T_{air} and T_{soil}) with future SM reflected the unique soil and ecological conditions across our case study sites. Crop A and Crop B, with their fertile organic topsoil and proximity to drainage features, showed statistically meaningful T correlations with

Fig. 5. The evaluation of HIST and FORENV scenarios for different land covers and lead times.

future SM. These areas, under agricultural use with plants for grazing and barley cultivation, experienced direct exposure to solar radiation and the influence of nearby drainage ditches, which could enhance the sensitivity of SM to T. Concerning forest land covers, Forest D with its coarse, rocky soil, and nearby drainage, supported a mixed tree canopy which allowed for some solar penetration, leading to a moderate response of SM to T changes. Conversely, Forest C, characterized by a peat layer and coarse-grained sandy soil without drainage, hosted a dense forest. This structure likely created a stable microclimate that buffered SM from the influences of T, contributing to the negligible correlation. The Forest_Peatland stations presented contrasting scenarios. For instance, station Forest_Peatland F, despite being a marshy peatland, showed a moderate to high T correlation. This may be due to differences in water levels between Forest_Peatland E and Forest_Peatland F. Specifically, Forest_Peatland F might have a lower water table compared to Forest_Peatland E. A lower water table leads to greater fluctuations in T_{soil} because the soil contains more air, which has lower thermal conductivity. This allows the soil to heat and cool more rapidly than water and reduces evaporative cooling, resulting in a stronger correlation between T_{soil} and SM (Khamidov et al., 2023). Similar

findings have been reported in other studies on peatland hydrology. For example, research by Price (1996) and Malloy & Price (2014) highlights that in decomposed peat with a lower water table, capillary forces can retain significant water content, but the presence of air-filled pores increases thermal variability, which in turn influences T_{soil} dynamics. Additionally, it has been observed that even minor water additions can raise water levels by tens of centimeters due to low specific yield values (Ronkanen & Kløve, 2005), suggesting that fluctuations in water table depth can rapidly alter SM and T_{soil} conditions. Furthermore, the study indicated that the thermal properties of decomposed peat allow it to retain moisture even with deeper groundwater levels. However, the presence of air in the soil with a lower water table results in a faster response to changes in T_{soil}. This is particularly relevant at the drained sites, where high water retention properties kept the soil wet even with fluctuating groundwater tables (Mustamo, 2017). Similarly, Price in Price (2003) emphasized that the capillary rise in decomposed peat allows for greater retention of water at depth, while simultaneously increasing T_{soil} variability due to lower thermal conductivity in drier peat layers. However, specific data on water table levels at both stations were not available in this study, and further research is needed to

Fig. 6. Evaluation of SM forecasting for different land cover groups’ datasets when trained with RF models. Each key denotes “feature group dataset/lead time SM forecasting”.

Table 6
The impact evaluation of individual SV parameters in conjunction with LaggedSM on SM forecasting.

Dataset/lead time SM forecasting	RMSE ($m^3 \cdot m^{-3}$)	R ²
LaggedSM_SV/SM _{t+1}	0.006	0.94
LaggedSM_T _{soil} /SM _{t+1}	0.006	0.94
LaggedSM_NDVI/SM _{t+1}	0.006	0.94
LaggedSM_SV/SM _{t+4}	0.014	0.82
LaggedSM_T _{soil} /SM _{t+4}	0.016	0.76
LaggedSM_NDVI/SM _{t+4}	0.015	0.79
LaggedSM_SV/SM _{t+7}	0.019	0.67
LaggedSM_T _{soil} /SM _{t+7}	0.022	0.61
LaggedSM_NDVI/SM _{t+7}	0.021	0.61

validate this hypothesis by incorporating detailed water table measurements. Such data could help clarify the extent to which water table fluctuations influence T_{soil} dynamics and their correlation with SM at

different depths.

The correlation analysis conducted in this study suggested that RH was not a predominant factor driving SM variability in subarctic regions. This was likely due to the consistently high baseline RH levels and the tendency of the soil towards saturation under typical regional P regimes. Our observations indicated that both annual and growing season average RH were relatively elevated (approximately 80 % and 78 %, respectively), while P rates were also significant (averaging nearly 700 mm annually and 500 mm during the growing season). Given the minor fluctuations in RH and the frequent near-saturation soil conditions, RH’s impact on SM was diminished, resulting in a low correlation. Additionally, the soil’s moisture content at a depth of 30 cm seems less immediately responsive to atmospheric RH compared to surface layers. The high P levels also further contributed to maintaining SM at or near saturation, limiting the influence of RH changes.

Contrary to expectations, the analysis revealed a surprisingly low to negligible P correlation, especially pronounced in Forest and Forest_Peatland environments compared to Crop regions. It should be noted that at the sub-surface SM measured depth (30 cm), SM might be buffered against immediate fluctuations in P due to several factors such as

soils' field capacity. While it is important to know the precise field capacity for each case study, the inherent spatial and temporal variability of the parameter, which can be influenced by factors such as soil structure, organic matter content, historical land use, and current vegetation patterns, would require extensive site-specific calibration and long-term monitoring. Such an effort, while beneficial, was beyond the scope of our current investigation. Thus, our interpretations were based on the soil textures' capacities extracted from our local investigations and OpenLandMap Soil Texture Class (USDA System) with 250-meter spatial resolution (https://stac.openlandmap.org/texture.class_usda.tt/collection.json?language=en) showing loam and sand-loam soils for the crop and forested stations (Gupta et al., 2020; Javidan et al., 2024), respectively. In the forested sites, the peat layer's high water retention ability might mean that the soil was often at or near saturation, thus additional rainfall had a minimal impact on SM. Moreover, the multi-layered canopy acted as an initial barrier to rainfall, with much of the moisture potentially being retained on foliage and subsequently evaporated, never reaching the soil surface (Fischer et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2019). The high average RH and P further suggested that the soil did not frequently dry out, reducing the incremental effect of P on SM. These could also be observed for Forest_Peatland sites. Even with a drainage ditch nearby, the peatlands' ability to remain wet and the generally high RH reduced the responsiveness of SM to additional P. In addition to the mentioned possible reasons, water management strategies employed by landowners in croplands can be effective. Specifically, in the absence of manual irrigation in subarctic regions, landowners may adopt drainage control practices aimed at conserving natural P within their fields. Such measures could effectively decouple the direct relationship between P events and the SM content detected at

a depth of 30 cm. Fig. 7, which shows the correlation between P_t and SM_{t+1} for selected sites, underscores the fact that despite precipitation playing a major role in the water budget, the measured response of SM at 30 cm can be considerably buffered by local soil and vegetation factors. Moreover, the minimal slope and dispersed points, especially at higher moisture levels, reflect the buffering capacity of peat layers, forest canopies, and near-saturation conditions in subarctic environments. An additional source of uncertainty arises from gridded precipitation datasets, which can fail to capture localized rainfall variability. While soil moisture is measured at a single point, precipitation data can be averaged over relatively large grid cells, leading to discrepancies in spatial resolution. As seen in Fig. 7, the correlation increases when transitioning from lower-resolution (OM) to higher-resolution (FMI) precipitation inputs. Intense, localized rainfall events may thus be misaligned with daily SM measurements, resulting in low or even negative correlations. Collectively, these findings explain why a simple linear correlation between daily P and the subsequent day's SM often appears low or minimal, given that near-saturation, interception, canopy evaporation, and delayed infiltration can all weaken the direct impact of rainfall on subsurface moisture.

For Crop stations compared to their counterparts, ET0 appeared to be more strongly correlated with future SM. In comparison with Forests and Forest_Peatlands covered by respective dense canopy and sphagnum moss, the croplands' soils were usually more directly exposed to solar radiation and wind, contributing to higher evaporation rates. Furthermore, farming practices, such as tillage, could augment the surface roughness of the soil, thereby amplifying the potential for ET.

Concerning WS, Crop stations exhibited an almost moderate correlation which can be due to more exposure to the wind compared to the

Fig. 7. Time-series plots illustrate the Pearson correlation (R) between daily precipitation (P_t) of FMI and OM data, and subsequent day's soil moisture (SM_{t+1}) at 30 cm for selected sites.

forested areas, thereby increasing ETO and subsequently reducing SM. For the forested stations, the observed correlations were low to negligible. The peat layer's high water retention ability, dense vegetation, and often sphagnum moss can hold moisture effectively in these areas, lessening the impact of wind on direct evaporation and SM levels.

The Crop stations showed stronger correlations between NDVI and future SM which could be due to the direct relationship between vegetation health and SM in agricultural settings. In croplands, plants are actively growing and are often more responsive to changes in SM, making NDVI a good proxy for predicting SM (Bandak et al., 2023). The NDVI in Forest D may not be as closely linked to future SM due to the variability in tree age and density, affecting the index's sensitivity to changes in SM. Moreover, the predominantly coarse-grained soil mixed with sandy components and rocks could lead to a complex interaction between NDVI and SM which is not detected in MODIS spatial resolution, potentially showing moderate correlations. Forest C, covered by a dense canopy of big trees, might display a lower correlation between NDVI and SM due to the canopy's ability to maintain a consistent level of humidity and SM underneath, which might not directly reflect in NDVI values. Additionally, the peat layer on top and coarse-grained sandy soil at 30 cm depth can retain water effectively, leading to less variation in SM than NDVI could detect. Forest_Peatland stations, with their distinct soil compositions that include peat and organic soil or a mixture of organic and sandy soil at depth and with varying proximity to drainage ditches, might also demonstrate weaker NDVI-SM correlations. The waterlogged conditions and dense vegetation in peatlands could lead to a decoupling of NDVI from SM, as the vegetation may not exhibit as much stress from SM variations due to the consistent wet conditions.

The observed strong correlations between $SM_{t/t-1}$ and future SM across the stations suggested that SM has a memory effect, where past moisture conditions were indicative of future conditions. Crop stations showed a great relationship possibly due to the fertile soils' capacity for water retention and release. The dense canopy in the Forest and the water-holding nature of the peat in Forest_Peatland also contribute to a consistent SM over time, reflecting in strong correlations. Given the high RH and P in these regions, along with measurements at a 30 cm depth, these environments exhibited a significant memory effect, allowing past SM to be a reliable predictor of future SM levels.

To determine the most and weakest relevant parameters in future SM forecasting based on Pearson correlation analysis, we averaged the correlation values obtained between each parameter and in-situ SM one-day (in-situ SM_{t+1}) lead time across all land covers. Results indicated that in-situ SM_t with the average correlation (ac) of 0.96 was the most relevant parameter, sequentially followed by in-situ SM_{t-1} (ac: 0.92), T_{soil} (ac: 0.48), NDVI (ac: 0.345), T_{air} (ac: 0.34), ETO (ac: 0.22), WS (ac: 0.14), RH (ac: 0.12), and P (ac: 0.11). These findings underscored the importance of the soil's water retention capacity and its memory effect, which can overshadow other environmental variables. T_{soil} , NDVI, and T_{air} demonstrated substantial to fair predictive relevance, respectively. Conversely, ETO, WS, RH showed weaker correlations, suggesting that while these factors contribute to SM processes, their predictive power is limited relative to the historical SM, T, and NDVI. Notably, P presented the weakest correlation which can reflect the unique characteristics of subarctic systems, where the high baseline SM content due to typically elevated RH and substantial annual P may reduce the incremental impact of rainfall events in SM fluctuations.

4.3. The best scenario

The increasing RMSE values and decreasing R^2 values for both scenarios with longer forecast lead times suggested a decline in predictive accuracy as the projection horizon extends into the future (Fig. 5). This phenomenon highlights the challenges inherent in forecasting SM over extended periods, likely due to the complex interplay of environmental factors influencing SM dynamics. The comparison between HIST and FORENV revealed that, across most sites, FORENV outperformed HIST

until $t + 4$, indicating the added value of incorporating forecasted variables in improving predictive accuracy in the short to medium term. However, beyond $t + 4$, the performance of HIST and FORENV diverged across different sites.

Fig. A2 showcased that the observed Pearson correlation trends between in-situ $SM_{t/t-1}$ and future in-situ SM aligned with the predictive performance disparities between HIST and FORENV, which can be employed to select the most efficient scenario for each site. A discernible pattern emerged where the intensity of correlation decreases correlated with the duration of HIST's superiority over FORENV. Specifically, at Crop A, where a minor decrease in correlation intensity was observed (maintaining at 0.9 by $t + 7$), HIST demonstrated sustained superior performance, indicative of the robustness of historical data in forecasting at this location. In contrast, sites such as Forest C and Forest_Peatland E, which exhibited a sharper decline in correlation to 0.48 and 0.65, respectively, showed a tendency for FORENV to provide more accurate predictions, underscoring the value of incorporating forecasted data in these sites. Furthermore, intermediate correlation declines at sites Crop B and Forest_Peatland F led to FORENV's superiority in the initial four days, whereas at site Forest D, with correlations in the 0.7 to 0.8 range, FORENV's forecasting accuracy extended to five days. These patterns suggested that sites with less intense correlation decreases lean towards HIST's historical data-based approach, while those with greater decreases benefited from FORENV's inclusion of forecasted environmental data. The results implied that while forecasted information may enhance short-term SM forecasting accuracy, the long-term performance of SM forecasting is closely tied to the consistency of historical SM correlation. This underscores the necessity of evaluating the dynamics of correlation between current/lagged and future SM values prior to selecting or adjusting forecasting models.

4.4. The most effective feature inputs

Fig. 6 clearly demonstrated the importance of LaggedSM data in improving SM forecasting accuracy across all lead times. Models that incorporated historical SM data consistently outperformed those that relied solely on climate or SV features. Specifically, for short-term forecasts (SM_{t+1}), the inclusion of LaggedSM data resulted in comparable performance across all feature groups. This suggests a possible saturation point where adding more features did not yield significant improvements for immediate lead times. As the forecast horizon extended to SM_{t+4} and SM_{t+7} , the LaggedSM_SV dataset exhibited noticeable improvements in performance, particularly in terms of R^2 , surpassing models that only included climate or SV data. This improvement can be attributed to the additional soil parameters contributing to moisture retention dynamics over longer periods. Conversely, datasets that solely included SV or climate features without historical SM data revealed the lowest performance metrics, highlighting the limited predictive utility of these datasets in SM forecasting.

Interestingly, the All_inputs dataset, which includes all available features, performed similarly to the LaggedSM inclusive groups, with LaggedSM_SV outperforming slightly at the longer lead times. This suggests that All_inputs may be largely redundant which can cause an increase of model complexity and a risk of overfitting, where the model becomes finely tuned to the training data at the expense of its generality. This observation indicates that simpler models incorporating LaggedSM data are sufficient for accurate SM forecasting, especially in regions with limited climatic or SV data availability. On the other hand, the individual analysis of T_{soil} and NDVI in conjunction with LaggedSM (Table 6) demonstrated that both variables provide valuable information for short-term forecasts. However, combining these SV parameters in the LaggedSM_SV dataset offered marginal improvements for longer-term forecasts.

Overall, the results highlighted the effectiveness of including historical SM data in SM forecasting models and suggested that even with limited data types, reliable forecasts can be achieved. These results were

consistent with the Pearson correlation outputs (Fig. 4) indicating LaggedSM data's highest correlations, followed by SV parameters, with future SM values. Moreover, Pan JinJing et al. (2019), Togneri et al. (2022), and Yu et al., (2021) showed LaggedSM data's highest performance in SM forecasting, being similar to our results.

The findings presented in this study offer insights into the uniqueness and novelty of SM forecasting in subarctic regions, distinguishing our approach from studies in more temperate or arid climates (Acharya et al., 2021; Gill et al., 2006; Kashyap et al., 2021; Maia et al., 2022; Ren et al., 2023; Zaman & McKee, 2014). Subarctic ecosystems, as encountered in Finland, are characterized by short growing seasons, frequent cloud cover, high baseline humidity, and often saturated soil conditions at critical rooting depths. These conditions fundamentally shape the relationship between environmental parameters and SM, as observed in the varying sensitivities of SM to T_{air} , T_{soil} , RH, and P across different land covers. The consistently elevated RH, substantial annual precipitation, and seasonal patterns in subarctic conditions result in a system where SM fluctuations may be more closely tied to soil retention properties and vegetation dynamics than to direct short-term changes in meteorological variables. Furthermore, the use of gridded climate datasets and forecasted environmental data, acquired from sources like OM and integrated into the FORENV scenario, enabled us to capture the influence of spatially continuous climate variables and realistically represent forward-looking conditions. This approach contrasts with station-based measurements (Acharya et al., 2021; Kashyap et al., 2021; Maia et al., 2022; Ren et al., 2023; Zaman & McKee, 2014), which may overlook spatial heterogeneities and limit the model's applicability at broader scales. By leveraging these gridded products, we demonstrated that accurate, near-real-time SM forecasts are feasible even under data-scarce conditions common to subarctic regions, ultimately enhancing the transferability and utility of the predictive framework in similar environments.

4.5. Uncertainties and limitations

Despite the promising results, several uncertainties and limitations warrant discussion. First, the dataset's limited temporal span, covering only two growing seasons (July or August 2022–September 2023), constrains the analysis to relatively short climatological cycles. Although this timeframe captures typical subarctic conditions, it may not encompass episodic or long-term climatic variability, such as unusually intense rainfall or extended drought periods. Future work could mitigate this constraint by incorporating longer historical records, thereby capturing a broader range of environmental scenarios.

Second, the use of gridded climate datasets (OM or ERA5), while essential in regions with sparse in-situ measurements, can introduce interpolation errors or fail to capture localized soil and canopy features such as microtopography, peat layers, or drainage networks. These small-scale spatial heterogeneities can significantly influence soil moisture processes, underscoring the potential benefit of integrating higher-resolution, locally validated climate products. Furthermore, our models' calibration relied on random splitting and K-fold cross-validation, which given the short data record and the absence of strict time-based splits may not fully account for temporal autocorrelation or serial dependencies. Extending the data span and adopting time-series-specific validation strategies such as rolling-origin splits could offer a more conservative estimate of model skill, especially at longer lead times beyond $t + 4$.

Another key limitation relates to the fixed measurement depth (30 cm) of soil moisture. While our findings are valuable for understanding sub-surface soil moisture and its day-to-day dynamics, many crops and vegetation species depend on moisture in shallower layers (e.g., top 10–20 cm), where root uptake is most intensive. Thus, measurements at 30 cm may not reflect the prompt moisture deficits that lead to immediate stress in the upper root zone. Additionally, the near-saturated state observed at 30 cm in many subarctic sites may dampen the

immediate influence of precipitation or relative humidity. This buffering effect can obscure the role of precipitation in driving short-term moisture changes and reduce the correlation signal particularly in peatland or forested areas with high water retention. Exploring different sensor depths or a vertical SM profile could yield insights into how deeper or shallower soil layers respond to environmental drivers.

Another source of uncertainty arises from our SARIMAX-based approach for forecasting NDVI. While short-term NDVI predictions (up to about $t + 4$) remained reasonably accurate, performance noticeably declined by $t + 5$ – $t + 7$, indicating higher error and lower correlation at longer horizons. This decline likely reflects the difficulty of capturing abrupt vegetative changes using primarily historical and seasonal trends. Although SARIMAX proves practical when plant-related data are sparse, incorporating more advanced or non-linear models might better anticipate rapid phenological changes and maintain accuracy beyond the four-day mark.

Lastly, the FORENV scenario introduces another layer of uncertainty. OM aggregates predictions from multiple weather models (e.g., ICON, GFS, HRRR), each with distinct spatial resolutions and possible interpolation errors. While combining these models improves short-to-medium-term accuracy, slight discrepancies in the climate features' forecasts can compound, especially over longer lead times. Consequently, soil moisture predictions in FORENV might under- or over-estimate actual water availability if the forecasted inputs diverge from real conditions. Testing an ensemble of forecast models or refining assimilation techniques might help reduce these uncertainties.

By acknowledging these sources of uncertainty and methodological limitations, we aim to set a foundation for subsequent research, emphasizing the potential of longer temporal datasets, higher-resolution climate inputs, multi-depth SM measurements, and more advanced forecast NDVI and climate data in enhancing the robustness and applicability of soil moisture forecasting under subarctic conditions.

5. Conclusions

This study assessed the potential of gridded historical and forecasted climate and soil data alongside gap-filled MODIS NDVI in improving SM forecasting in subarctic regions. To this end, two scenarios were defined: one using only historical data (HIST) and the other by incorporating forecasted environmental data along with recent SM measurements (FORENV), both analyzed through RF models. Moreover, the importance of different input features was evaluated by Pearson correlation analysis and a stepwise forward RF-based feature selection technique.

The results demonstrated that utilizing gridded climate datasets was a promising alternative for SM forecasting in regions with scarce in-situ data. The comparative analysis of the scenarios revealed that FORENV consistently delivers better performance than HIST within a four-day forecasting window at most locations. This underscored the value of including forecast variables to enhance forecast accuracy in the short to medium term, though long-term forecast performance remained site-dependent and was affected by the constancy of historical SM correlations. These findings emphasized the importance of pre-assessing the correlations between past/existing and upcoming SM levels to effectively select forecasting strategies for different situations. Through Pearson correlation analysis and stepwise forward RF-based feature selection, it was determined that the LaggedSM dataset, either alone or combined with SV attributes, can achieve appropriate forecasts. This suggested that models based solely on historical SM data can yield dependable forecasts, which proved especially advantageous in areas lacking detailed climatic or SV data.

In the future, in-situ or gridded environmental datasets of stations with different climate conditions can be used as inputs to various ML models, including those based on deep learning techniques, for SM forecasting to evaluate the proposed scenarios and globally determine the most efficient SM forecasting strategy, model, and inputs. Additionally, developing this methodology into an Android software

application could provide real-time support for farmers and decision-makers in managing agricultural irrigation water more efficiently.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mojtaba Saboori: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Kedar Surendranath Ghag:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **Anandharuban Panchanathan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Epari Ritesh Patro:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **Ali Torabi Haghighi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Fig. A1. The process of NDVI gap filling conducted for Crop A.

Fig. A2. Comparison between Pearson correlation analysis obtained for observed lagged/current and future SM (the heatmap palette embedded below each line chart) and forecasted SM achieved for different scenarios to select the best scenario for each site.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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